

Studies on Acetamide Derivatives. Part-II. Preparation, Antimicrobial and Anthelmintic Activity of *N*-Arylaminoacetylbenzimidazole/sulphadiazine or sulphamethazine and *N*-Arylbenzimidazol-1-yl/sulphadiazin- 4-yl or sulphamethazin-4-yl/acetamides

V. H. SHAH, N. A. CHAUHAN and A. R. PARIKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot 360 005

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We have synthesised *N*-arylaminoacetylbenzimidazole/sulphadiazine or sulphamethazine by the condensation of *N*-chloroacetylbenzimidazole or 4-*N*-chloroacetyl-sulphadiazine derivatives with different aromatic amines. *N*-Arylbenzimidazol-1-yl/sulphadiazin-4-yl- or sulphamethazine-4-yl-acetamides were also obtained by the condensation of benzimidazole or sulphadiazine derivatives with *N*-chloroacetylated arylamines. The products were screened for antimicrobial and anthelmintic activities. The constitution of the product was supported by ir spectra and elemental analysis.

IN continuation of our work on acetamide derivatives¹, we have synthesised acetamide derivatives of type 1-4. The *N*-arylaminoacetylbenzimidazoles (1) were obtained by the condensation of *N*-chloroacetylbenzimidazole with aromatic amines². 4-*N*-Arylaminoacetyl-sulphadiazine or -sulphamethazine (2) were obtained by the condensation of 4-*N*-chloroacetylsulphadiazine^{3,4} or 4-*N*-chloroacetylsulphamethazine^{3,4} with aromatic amines. The *N*-arylbenzimidazol-1-ylacetamides (3) were synthesised by the condensation of benzimidazole^{5,6} with the different *N*-chloroacetylated aromatic amines (5). The *N*-arylsulphadiazin-4-yl/sulphamethazin-4-ylacetamides (4) were obtained by the condensation of sulphadiazine¹ or sulphamethazine with different *N*-chloroacetylated aromatic amines¹.

5, R.NH.COCH₂Cl

R = Aryl, R' = H or OH.

The constitution of the products (1-4) was supported by ir spectra (KBr). The ir spectra of the compounds show the following characteristic

bands for acetamide derivatives having benzimidazole moiety of type 1 and 3 at 1 625, 1 675, 1 680 (α -C=O tertiary amide stretch) and 2 875, 3 175, 3 305 and 3 315 cm⁻¹ (NH...N polymeric association through intermolecular H-bond), whereas acetamide derivatives having sulphadiazine moiety of type 2 and 4 at 1 680-1 700 (α -C=O second amide stretch), 1 140-1 170 (NH.SO₂)⁸ and 950 cm⁻¹ (pyrimidine ring)⁹.

Antibacterial, antifungal, anthelmintic activity: The products were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using DMF as a solvent at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ by cup-plate method¹⁰. They were also tested¹¹ for anthelmintic activity against (earthworms) *pheretima posthuma* taking 10.0 mg of different products with Tween-80 and 20 00 ml of modified Ringer solution¹² and an earthworm duly acclimated. Time required to paralyse or kill all the worms were noted by applying a slight stimulus (Table 1) as compared with piperazine citrate.

Experimental

4-Chloroacetylaminosulphadiazine: Chloroacetylchloride (11.4 g, 0.1 mol) and sulphadiazine (25.00 g, 0.1 mol) in sodium-dried benzene (100 ml, thiophene-free) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 235° (Found: N, 17.10; S, 9.75. C₁₂H₁₁N₄O₂SCl requires: N, 17.15; S, 9.79%).

Similarly, sulphamethazine and benzimidazole were chloroacetylated with chloroacetyl chloride: sulphamethazine (78%), m.p. 170° (Found: N,

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TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-4*

Sl. no.	R	R ¹	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity (24 h)		Anthelmintic activity Average time to paralyse or kill all worms
					Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm		
					<i>S. aureus</i> 24 h	<i>E. coli</i> 24 h	
<i>N</i> -Arylaminoacetylbenzimidazole (1)							
1.	Phenyl	—	75	63	18	—	—
2.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	70	65	19	6	3.5
3.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	86	62	17	—	3.5
4.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	125	60	17	—	> 3.5
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	—	180	55	15	—	> 8
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	—	145	70	15	6	> 8
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	—	131	72	15	—	4.5
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	—	150	52	15	—	> 4
9.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	—	140	59	11	—	> 8
10.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	—	155	56	11	—	> 8
<i>N</i> -Arylbenzimidazol-1-ylacetamides (3)							
11.	Phenyl	—	110	65	18	—	4
12.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	125	68	20	—	> 8
13.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	142	60	20	—	> 8
14.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	260D	62	20	—	> 8
15.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	—	205	70	22	6	4
16.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	—	75	55	22	—	> 8
17.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	—	286D	52	22	—	7
18.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	—	230	56	14	—	4
19.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	—	105	59	25	6	> 8
20.	Cyclohexyl	—	120	57	25	6	> 8
21.	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	—	101	61	20	—	4
4- <i>N</i> -(Arylaminoacetyl)sulphadiazine/sulphamethazine (2)							
22.	Phenyl	H	220	55	21	7	> 8
23.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	212	60	20	7	4
24.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	225	57	20	7	4
25.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	140	51	20	—	4
26.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	228	52	20	—	5.5
27.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	110	54	8	—	6
28.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	180	55	15	—	6
29.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	242	45	15	—	> 8
30.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	H	212	47	15	—	> 8
31.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	207	48	15	9	> 8
32.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	115	61	19	9	4
33.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	139	63	19	9	> 8
34.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	220	64	19	—	> 8
35.	α -Naphthyl	H	228	60	17	—	> 8
36.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	H	183	59	17	—	> 8
37.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	H	175	55	17	—	> 8
38.	Cyclohexyl	H	105	59	12	—	4.5
39.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	190	60	12	—	6.5
40.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	220	63	12	12	7
41.	Phenyl	OH ₂	86	64	20	—	7
42.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH ₂	210	57	20	—	7
43.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH ₂	253	60	20	12	> 4.5
44.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH ₂	215	65	20	14	> 4.5
45.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	OH ₂	115	68	19	14	4.5
46.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	OH ₂	206	57	19	—	4.5
47.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	OH ₂	220	59	19	—	5.5
48.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	OH ₂	90	55	16	—	> 8
49.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	OH ₂	105	57	16	—	> 8
50.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	OH ₂	150	59	16	10	> 8
51.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH ₂	96	60	18	9	> 8
52.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH ₂	105	63	18	9	> 8
53.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH ₂	180	70	18	9	4.5
54.	α -Naphthyl	OH ₂	205	74	20	—	5.5
55.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	OH ₂	202	55	—	—	> 6
56.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	OH ₂	186	57	8	—	> 6
57.	Cyclohexyl	OH ₂	196	68	20	—	> 8
58.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	OH ₂	210	70	20	6	> 8
59.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	OH ₂	219	72	20	6	> 8
60.	Piperazine citrate	—	—	—	—	—	3.5
61.	Control	—	—	—	—	—	> 8

(Table 1 contd.)

N-Arylsulphadiazin-4-yl/sulphamethazin-4-ylacetamides (4)

62.	Phenyl	H	170	55	22	—	7
63.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	85	60	20	5	> 8
64.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	115	57	20	5	> 8
65.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	150	51	20	5	> 8
66.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	100	52	21	—	5
67.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	245	54	21	—	7
68.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	135	55	21	5	6
69.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	180	45	25	10	4.5
70.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	H	192	47	25	10	4.5
71.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	240	48	25	10	> 8
72.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	135	61	20	8	4
73.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	180	68	23	10	3.5
75.	3,5-Dichlorophenyl	H	240	64	23	10	> 8
76.	β -Naphthyl	H	150	60	23	8	3.5
78.	Phenyl	OH ₂	175	39	21	5	3.5
79.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH ₂	62	55	20	—	5
80.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH ₂	88	39	20	—	6
81.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH ₂	150	60	8	10	> 8
82.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	OH ₂	85	63	17	10	> 8
83.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	OH ₂	105	64	17	10	7
84.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	OH ₂	152	57	17	—	5
85.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	OH ₂	190	60	21	5	5
87.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	OH ₂	200	65	21	10	> 8
87.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	OH ₂	70	68	15	10	> 8
88.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH ₂	62	59	15	10	4.5
89.	β -Naphthyl	OH ₂	82	57	20	6	> 8

N-Chloroacetylarylamines of type R-NHCOCH₂Cl where R = Aryl (5)

90.	Phenyl	—	93	74	20	8	> 8
91.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	92	82	24	—	> 8
92.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	102	81	24	—	3.5
93.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	185	81	24	—	3.5
94.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	—	104	74	18	15	> 8
95.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	—	80	72	18	15	> 8
96.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	—	62	81	18	—	> 8
97.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	—	32	80	23	8	> 8
98.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	—	70	78	23	8	> 8
99.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	—	169	77	20	8	3
100.	3,5-Dichlorophenyl	—	123	75	20	—	4
103.	β -Naphthyl	—	158	79	15	—	4
103.	Cyclohexyl	—	106	74	15	—	4
104.	2-Ethoxyphenyl	—	71	79	15	—	4

*All compounds gave correct C, H, N analysis.

15.75; S, 9.00. C₁₄H₁₃N₄O₂SCl requires: N, 15.80; S, 9.03%; benzimidazole (45%), m.p. 135° (Found: N, 14.33. C₉H₇N₂OCl requires: N, 14.40%).

4-(Phenylaminoacetyl)sulphadiazine: 4-Chloroacetylsulphadiazine (3.27 g, 0.01 mol) and aniline (0.93 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml, 99.5%) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (55%), m.p. 220° (Found: N, 18.25; S, 8.34. C₁₆H₁₇N₇O₂S₂ requires: N, 18.28; S, 8.35%).

Similarly, 4-chloroacetylsulphamethazine and *N*-chloroacetylbenzimidazole were condensed with different aromatic amines. The physical data are recorded in Table 1.

N-Phenylbenzimidazol-1-ylacetamide: Benzimidazole (0.01 mol) and *N*-chloroacetyl aromatic base (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml; 99.5%) were refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 110°

(Found: N, 16.70. C₁₄H₁₃N₃O requires: N, 16.73%).

Similarly, sulphadiazine or sulphamethazine were condensed with *N*-chloroacetylphenylamine. The physical data are recorded in Table 1.

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